

Assessing the Assessment Literacy of Mathematics Teachers in Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract:

The study investigated the assessment literacy of mathematics teachers in Southwest, Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to determine the level of assessment literacy of mathematics teachers in secondary schools. The study also investigated the exposure of mathematics teachers to assessment training. The descriptive research design of the survey type was adopted. The sample for the study consisted of 700 mathematics teachers selected through the multistage sampling technique from selected secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. Two research questions were raised and two hypotheses were generated for the study. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The result from the teachers' responses showed that the level of assessment literacy of mathematics teachers was low despite their exposure to assessment training. However, gender and years of teaching experience does not influence the assessment literacy of mathematics teachers in secondary schools.

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Introduction

In secondary schools, students and teachers encounter classroom and non-classroom interactions. Such interactions usually define the school curriculum. In the course of these interactions, teachers endeavour to determine what students have learnt and are capable of learning. This is otherwise known as assessment. Assessment can be described as a systematic process of gathering information about what a student knows, does or learns. The term, assessment, is used to describe some of the ways by which teachers determine the learning experiences or outcomes of students. Assessment enables teachers to find out what students know and are capable of doing at a particular time. In other words, assessment helps teachers to identify or diagnose students' learning needs, design and implement instructional strategies (Frey, 2014).

Assessment is a tool in education that is of great benefit to both students and teachers. As noted by Soto and DeManilla (2015), the information gathered during assessment can be used by teachers to improve instruction or to summarize students' achievement and monitor their learning. This implies that assessment have some crucial roles to play when it comes to the process of instruction delivery. These roles could be in terms of development or accountability. Assessment has a developmental function when the results are used to inform instruction. It has an accountability function when it summarizes what students have learnt overtime. Thus, there is a short-term and long-term forms of assessment. Summarily, assessment of students in the classroom could be categorized into two major forms: formative assessment and summative assessment. Formative assessment determines learning progression and also corrects learning errors while summative assessment is designed to provide information on the performance of students at the end of the term/session.

Assessment in the classroom should be made comprehensive enough for decision making. In view of this, mathematics teachers need to be vast in the various assessment techniques that can be used to obtain information from the students. This was emphasized by Ayoola (2019). Witte (2010) also pointed out that classroom assessment should be an official tool every teacher needs to be armed with as expected in their professional practice. Classroom assessment matters a lot when it comes to students' achievement, most especially in Mathematics. Students' achievement (particularly those that are below average) tend to improve when they are actively engaged in the assessment process.

Teacher assessment literacy incorporates teacher's knowledge of the subject matter and how the teacher could transform such knowledge in order to improve students' performance (including thinking skills, manipulative skills, attitude and emotions) in mathematics. Oluwatayo and Bandele (2013) defines assessment literacy as the knowledge and skills acquired by a teacher to identify and use the appropriate assessment techniques to gather accurate evidence of students' learning. Thus, assessment literacy of teachers is very vital to the overall performance of students in any academic task, especially Mathematics. Little wonder, Deneen and Brown (2016) strongly affirmed that any teacher (irrespective of the

status) that refuses to update his/her knowledge of assessment techniques is committing a professional suicide.

Since it has been proven that a good assessment improves students' achievement and provide skilled teacher direction (Stiggins, 2004), emphasis should then be laid on the quality of assessment training received by the teachers. This is due to the fact that the training received by a teacher on classroom assessment may likely influence the assessment techniques exhibited by such teacher. This tends to improve teacher assessment literacy. The process of becoming assessment literate is transformative, conscious – evoking one, as noted by Xu and Brown (2017). However, it is quite unfortunate that many pre – service teacher education programmes hardly provide the needed expertise for effective classroom assessment. Greenberg and Walsh (2012) noted that colleges only offer a one – semester course that provides a general introduction to assessment. The resultant effect is that teachers' knowledge on classroom assessment may be narrow and thus, be incompetent in terms of assessment literacy. Pedagogically, teachers, irrespective of their gender or years of teaching experience, are expected to be assessment literate so as to be able to select the appropriate source of information, ensure accurate judgements and also determine the purpose of assessment (Bandeke & Oluwatayo, 2013).

It appears there are problems associated with mathematics teachers' assessment literacy. Teachers' knowledge of assessment techniques appears to be narrow and restrictive; and this is preventing the teachers from having accurate and comprehensive information about the students. Teachers do not use the right assessment technique to obtain the right information from students and this is affecting the performance of students in mathematics. The study determined the level of assessment literacy of mathematics teachers. The study also investigated the exposure of mathematics teachers to assessment training. The study further examined the influence of gender and years of teaching experience on assessment literacy of mathematics teachers.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for the study:

1. Are mathematics teachers exposed to classroom assessment training?
2. What is the level of assessment literacy possessed by mathematics teachers?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Gender has no significant influence on mathematics teachers' assessment literacy.
2. Years of teaching experience have no significant influence on mathematics teachers' assessment literacy.

Methodology

The study employed the descriptive research of survey type in order to describe the assessment literacy of mathematics teachers in public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. Participants were 700 mathematics teachers selected from 198 public secondary schools in Ekiti, Oyo and Lagos States using the multistage sampling technique. A self developed instrument tagged 'Mathematics Teachers Assessment Literacy Test' was used for data collection. The instrument is in two sections: section A dealt with the bio-data of the respondents including gender (male/female), years of teaching experience, number of times exposed to assessment training. Section B contained 30 multiple choice items on teachers' knowledge of various assessment techniques. The reliability coefficient of section B was estimated at 0.69 using Kuder – Richardson 21 (KR_{21}) formula. Data collected were analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, mean scores, t - test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

Results

Question 1: Are mathematics teachers exposed to classroom assessment training?

Data were analyzed using frequency counts and percentages as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Frequency Counts and Percentages of Mathematics Teachers In - service Classroom Assessment Training

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Teachers with in - service exposure to classroom assessment training	679	97.0
Teachers without in - service exposure to classroom assessment training	21	3.0
Total	700	100.0

Table 1 shows that 679 teachers representing 97% indicated their exposure to in - service assessment training while 21 teachers representing 3% indicated non - exposure to in - service classroom assessment training. This implies that substantial percentage of mathematics teachers had exposure to in - service training on classroom assessment.

Question 2: What is the level of assessment literacy of mathematics teachers?

The level was categorized into 'high', 'moderate' and 'low' using mean and standard deviation of the scores in Assessment Literacy Test. Respondents who scored 0-7 of the total score on classroom assessment literacy were categorized into "Low" literacy level while those who scored 8 - 15, 16 and above of the total score were grouped into "Moderate" and "High" literacy levels respectively. The highest boundary of each of the intervals was determined using the mean score of 10.9 and standard deviation of 3.9. The highest interval of the low

level was obtained by $10.9 - 3.9 = 7$. The highest interval for the moderate level was obtained by $10.9 + 3.9 = 14.8$ and this was approximated to 15. The frequency counts and percentages of the categories are as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Level of Mathematics Teachers' Assessment Literacy

Levels	Scores	Frequency	Percentage
High	16 - 30	68	9.7
Moderate	8 - 15	159	22.7
Low	0 - 7	473	67.6
Total		700	100.0

Table 2 shows that 68 teachers representing 9.7% of the total sample had high level of assessment literacy, 159(22.7%) had moderate level while 473(67.6%) had low level of assessment literacy. This implies that the assessment literacy of mathematics teachers is low.

Hypothesis 1: Gender has no significant influence on assessment literacy of mathematics teachers

Scores relating to assessment literacy were computed using Item 1-30 of Mathematics Teachers Assessment Literacy Test. These scores were compared for statistical significance using t-test at 0.05 level based on gender. The result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: t-test teachers' assessment literacy by gender

Sex	N	Mean	SD	Df	t	p
Male	262	11.42	5.20	698	1.344	0.180
Female	438	10.92	4.49			

$p > 0.05$

Table 3 reveals that there is no significant difference between the assessment literacy of male and female teachers ($t=1.344$, $p > 0.05$).

Hypothesis 2: Years of teaching experience have no significant influence on assessment literacy of mathematics teachers

Scores relating to assessment literacy were computed using Item 1-30 of Mathematics Teachers Assessment Literacy Test. These scores were compared for statistical significance

using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) statistics at 0.05 level based on years of teaching experience of Mathematics teachers. The result is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Mathematics teachers' assessment literacy by years of teaching experience

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p
Between Groups	2.394	2	1.197	.080	.923
Within Groups	10449.290	697	14.992		
Total	10451.684	699			

p>0.05

Table 4 reveals the years of teaching experience of a mathematics teacher will not significantly influence his/her assessment literacy skills ($F_{2,697}=0.080$, $p>0.05$).

Discussion

The findings from this study showed that over 90% of the mathematics teachers had exposure to classroom assessment training. This is quite interesting but unfortunately the outcome of the training did not reflect in their performance in the assessment literacy test designed for the study. The deduction that one could make from this is that mathematics teachers were only trying to cover up their deficiencies in assessment literacy but blindly indicated their participation in assessment literacy skills. This result tallies with the findings of Koloï- Keaikitse (2011) that teachers were unsure about the adequacy of their assessment training, but indicated that they needed further training in assessment. In the present study, there was indication of assessment training but the results in assessment literacy nullified the teachers' claim as over 67% of them scored lowly in Assessment Literacy Test.

Results in table 3 showed that gender had no significant influence on assessment literacy of mathematics teachers. This result is at variance with that of Alsarimi (2010), Alkharusi, et al (2012) and Mohiuddin (2015) who found that gender had significant influence on assessment literacy of teachers in favour of the male. The present study however holds that if assessment techniques are not emphasized during assessment training, both gender would be almost at the same level in assessment literacy as could be seen in the result of this study.

Years of teaching experience of mathematics teachers had no significant influence on their assessment literacy. Teachers with teaching experience of years ranging from eight years and above are expected to possess high assessment literacy level but the performance of teachers in the Assessment Literacy Test showed that teachers are relatively at the same level. This result also support the assertion made by Alsarimi (2010) that the years of teaching experience of teachers did not influence their assessment literacy.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it could be concluded that mathematics teachers' assessment literacy is low despite their claim that they had training on classroom assessment. Also, teacher assessment literacy is not influenced by gender and years of teaching experience.

Recommendations

1. There is need for regular training of mathematics teachers on classroom assessment to foster their level of literacy. This will widen their knowledge and expose them to various classroom assessment techniques. It will also promote quality assurance in mathematics lessons.
2. Teachers should be encouraged to equip themselves with various assessment techniques using relevant textbooks and the internet so as to bridge the gap between teacher assessment literacy and the training received on assessment.
3. Mathematics teachers should be trained freely irrespective of gender and years of teaching experience in order to have in – depth knowledge on classroom assessment techniques.

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